

INTEGRATED REMEDIATION STRATEGIES FOR URBAN AND INDUSTRIAL POLLUTION: INSIGHTS AND APPLICATIONS IN THE INCEL PROJECT

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Abstract: This study investigates the environmental and public health implications of soil contamination in the Incel industrial zone, Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina, focusing on polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and heavy metals. Recognized as a significant threat due to their persistence, bioaccumulation potential, and toxic effects, these pollutants have been extensively analyzed in the Incel area, a former cellulose factory repurposed as an industrial complex. The comprehensive assessment revealed alarmingly high concentrations of PCBs, exceeding national and international safety thresholds, alongside PAHs and heavy metals, indicating a severe contamination level that poses risks to human health and the local ecosystem. The methodology encompassed quality assurance mechanisms, standard operation procedures, and environmental protection measures, with a detailed investigation conducted across identified hotspots. This investigation, aligned with the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants’ directives, underscores the urgent need for remediation strategies to address the identified contamination. The project highlights the necessity of international cooperation and regulation in tackling such environmental challenges, emphasizing the role of robust environmental governance in safeguarding public health and ecosystems. This endeavor represents a pioneering initiative in the Republic of Srpska, marking the first comprehensive effort to mitigate soil contamination by hazardous substances such as PCBs. Through this project, the Incel industrial zone serves as a critical case study, demonstrating the effective integration of scientific research with remediation practices to address industrial contamination legacy. The findings contribute significantly to the global discourse on industrial pollution management and environmental restoration, offering insights and models for future remediation projects.

Key words: PCB, Incel, Banja Luka, pollution, remediation

INTRODUCTION

Polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), a group of POPs represent a category of synthetic organic compounds previously utilized extensively as insulating materials, coolants, and lubricants within electrical apparatus. These compounds are notably persistent, toxic, and prone to bioaccumulation, indicating their ability to persist in the environment for extended periods and to progressively concentrate within the food chain. The presence of PCBs poses significant risks to both environmental health and human well-being, due to their adverse effects (Gašić et al., 2010; Ilić et al., 2020; Ilić et al., 2021c; Ilić et al., 2023). PCBs have been identified in urban atmospheres across cities in North America, Western

Europe, and former Yugoslavia, with variations in sources and concentrations suggesting localized urban inputs as significant contributors (Gašić et al., 2010; APOPSBAL, 2019).

Research conducted by Ilić et al. (2021a; 2021b; 2021c; 2021d) has provided insight into the source identification and ecological risk assessment of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) and PCBs in soils and groundwater within industrial zones. The contamination at the Incel industrial area in Banja Luka (Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina) presents a critical concern for both the environment and public health, as highlighted by research from Ilić et al., 2020 and Stojanović Bjelić et al., 2022. Located approximately 3 km from the city center of Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina’s second-largest city, the Incel site (a former cellulose factory now repurposed as an industrial complex) exhibits extensive soil pollution. Investigations reveal varying concentrations of hazardous substances within the site’s soil, including polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), total petroleum hydrocarbons (TPHs), and heavy metals, confirming the area’s high level of pollution (Ilić et al., 2020; Ilić et al., 2021a; Ilić et al., 2021b; Ilić et al., 2021c; Ilić et al., 2021d; Ilić et al., 2023). The presence of PCBs and other detrimental pollutants has significantly compromised the quality of the soil, water, and air in the area, thus endangering human health and the surrounding ecosystem. These studies emphasize the pervasive nature of these contaminants and their potential sources, including volatilization from soil as a significant pathway for organochlorine pesticides in urban environments (Lammel et al., 2011). The variability in PAH levels and their mass size distributions across small spatial and temporal scales further illustrates the complexity of urban and industrial pollution landscapes (Lammel et al., 2010a; 2010b).

These findings underscore the importance of targeted remediation strategies to mitigate urban PCB emissions effectively. Moreover, the critical role of air quality in maintaining biodiversity within urban and industrial settings is highlighted by Ilić and Maksimović (2021), pointing towards the intricate relationship between pollution and ecological health.

Addressing heavy metal contamination, (Ilić et al. (2020)) identify new ‘hotspot’ areas within industrial zones, underscoring the ongoing risk to environmental and human health (Stojanović Bjelić et al., 2022). The need for stringent regulation and remediation values for pollutants in soil is echoed in the Rulebook (2021), which sets a legal framework for environmental protection efforts.

The Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (Lallas, 2001) provides an international legal basis for the global effort to eliminate or restrict the production and use of POPs, including PCBs and PAHs. This con-

vention underlines the importance of international cooperation and regulation in addressing the challenges posed by these hazardous substances. The Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) represents a global effort, established through an international agreement, to safeguard human health and the environment from the adverse effects of highly toxic and enduring chemicals like PCBs (Fiedler et al., 2019; Ilić and Maksimović, 2021). This issue of soil contamination by PCBs is intrinsically linked to the aims of the Stockholm Convention, considering that soil acts as a primary repository for these pollutants. The potential for contaminated soil to introduce PCBs into the food chain and their long-lasting presence in the environment underscores the risk they pose. The convention outlines a strategy for tackling soil contamination by POPs, including PCBs, advocating for risk assessments, the remediation of contaminated soils, and the prevention of pollution. The adoption of the convention’s guidelines enables nations to mitigate the hazards associated with soil contamination by PCBs and other POPs, thereby ensuring the protection of human health and the ecological system (Lallas, 2001; Porta & Zumeta, 2002; Fiedler et al., 2019; Ilić and Maksimović, 2021). This framework is particularly relevant to remediation projects like that in the Incel industrial zone, where addressing soil contamination is critical to complying with international standards for environmental protection and public health safety. The remediation project for the Incel industrial zone not only aligns with the global environmental protection efforts as outlined by the Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) but also represents a pioneering initiative in the Republic of Srpska. It stands as the first project of its kind within the region to comprehensively address soil contamination by hazardous substances such as PCBs. This groundbreaking endeavour sets a precedent for environmental remediation, emphasizing the importance of safeguarding human health and the ecosystem from the adverse effects of persistent pollutants. By undertaking such a significant project, the Republic of Srpska demonstrates a commitment to adhering to international environmental standards and contributes to the global effort to mitigate the risks associated with soil contamination by POPs. This initiative not only aims to remediate the contaminated soil in the Incel industrial zone but also serves as a model for future projects within the Republic and potentially beyond, highlighting the critical role of collaborative efforts in environmental protection and public health preservation.

Through the lens of these studies and regulations, our project in INCEL aims to adopt a comprehensive and informed approach to remediation, leveraging scientific research to guide our practices and policies. The integration of these findings into our project design is pivotal for the successful remediation

of contaminated sites, ensuring a sustainable and healthy environment for future generations.

In the contemporary era, the intersection of urbanization and industrial activities has posed significant environmental challenges, notably in the form of persistent organic pollutants (POPs) and heavy metal contamination. The project of remediation and recultivation in INCEL, Banja Luka, stands as a testament to the urgent need for addressing these environmental concerns. This introduction aims to outline the research findings and methodologies that inform our approach to remediation, emphasizing the significance of understanding pollutant sources, distribution, and ecological risks.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Macro-location

Banja Luka is the second largest city in Bosnia and Herzegovina. It is located in the north-western part of the country, and is the administrative centre of the Republika Srpska entity. It covers 1.238,91 km², with about 185.000 inhabitants. The town is situated on both banks of the Vrbas river, in a tectonic valley in the northeast-southwest direction, which is separated from Lijevce polje (Lijevce field) in Posavina by the Laktaska klisura. The city itself covers an area of 150 km², and is located at 44°46' north latitude and 17°11' east longitude. The average altitude of the urban area of Banja Luka settlement is 164 meters. The position of the municipality of Banja Luka in relation to BiH, i.e. the location to which the subject of this project is given is given on Figure 1.

Figure 1 Macro-location Banja Luka, “Business Zone” Incel

Micro Location

The micro-location of this project is the „Business Zone“ INCEL, which is located on the east bank of the Vrbas River, about 3 km from the center of Banja Luka, at 44°46'27" north latitude and 17°11'25" east longitude. The area of the location is approximately 65.65 ha, with an average altitude of approximately 155 m. The number of employees who perform daily activities and operations at the location is about 1,500, with about 1,500 visitors. This complex is located on the right bank of the river Vrbas in the alluvial plain. Its position in the city of Banja Luka is presented in Figure 2a. A detailed view of the entire micro-location, i.e., the „Business Zone“ INCEL itself, is given in Figure 2b.

Figure 2 a) Position of the location of the “Business Zone” INCEL about the city of Banja Luka; b) Micro-location Banja Luka, Incel

Methodology for the remediation and recultivation

The methodology for the remediation and recultivation of the INCEL site in Banja Luka, includes a comprehensive approach emphasizing quality assurance, stakeholder engagement, and environmental protection. This methodology is implemented through a series of carefully planned activities, ensuring that the remediation process adheres to high standards of environmental safety and efficacy. Key aspects of this methodology include:

1. Quality Assurance Mechanisms: To ensure the remediation project’s success, all processes are conducted under controlled conditions that align with the best international standards. This involves adhering to approved project documentation and employing proper methodologies

executed by qualified personnel, thus guaranteeing the final outputs’ stable quality.

2. **Standard Operation Procedures:** The project emphasizes the importance of following Standard Operation Procedures for site sampling, analysis, monitoring, and investigation. This standardization ensures consistent quality and reliability of the remediation work.
3. **Site Visits:** Regular and non-regular site visits are proposed as part of the internal control measures to assess the progress of remediation works. These visits allow for real-time evaluation and adjustment of the project’s execution to ensure alignment with the set objectives and standards.
4. **Short-term Preventive Measures:** Before the commencement of the actual remediation, short-term preventive measures are implemented to minimize human health risks at contaminated sites (hotspots). These measures are crucial for immediate risk mitigation until long-term and permanent remedial actions are executed.
5. **Project Implementation:** The project is segmented into specific activities, from preparatory works and site setup to final soil monitoring and backfilling. Each activity is detailed in subsequent chapters of the document, offering a clear technical description of the selected technologies and procedures involved.
6. **Environmental Protection Measures:** The methodology also includes a thorough evaluation of the environmental impacts of the remediation activities, with a detailed list of potential impacts and corresponding mitigation measures. This aspect underscores the project’s commitment to minimizing its environmental footprint and protecting the surrounding ecosystem.
7. **Waste Management:** A significant focus is placed on the handling of waste generated during the project, including identification of waste types, treatment methods, and adherence to European Waste Codes. This ensures that all waste is managed in an environmentally sound manner, adhering to local and international regulations.
8. **Professional Supervision and Monitoring:** The methodology includes measures for professional supervision to oversee the remediation process. These measures emphasize the verification of milestones, monitoring and reporting accuracy, and the implementation of quality assurance. These measures are essential for maintaining the project’s integrity and effectiveness.

This holistic approach, detailed in the Project/Design of Remediation and Recultivation for INCEL, Banja Luka (2021), combines rigorous quality assurance, environmental protection, and stakeholder engagement strategies, ensuring that the remediation and recultivation of the INCEL site are conducted to the highest standards.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Incel industrial zone in Banja Luka has been identified as a site with significant environmental and public health risks due to the high levels of PCBs found in the soil, alongside other pollutants like PAHs and heavy metals. These findings are concerning due to the well-documented risks PCBs pose to human health and their ability to remain in the environment for extended periods (Dorea, 2006; Srogi, 2008; EFSA et al., 2018). Industrial zones, particularly older ones such as Incel, are at a high risk for contaminating soil with these substances due to past practices before stricter chemical use regulations were established. Notably, PCBs, used in electrical equipment and other applications, were banned in the 1970s and 1980s, but their legacy remains a challenge (Gašić et al., 2010; Ilić et al., 2021c).

Recent assessments have revealed alarmingly high PCB concentrations at Incel, with levels reaching up to 400,000 ng/g (400 mg/kg) in dry soil samples, significantly surpassing levels at other sites (Apoposal, 2019; Ilić et al., 2021c). These concentrations, alongside the presence of heavy metals and other hazardous materials, necessitate urgent remediation efforts. The total PCBs concentrations found ranged from 0.26 to 6,722 mg/kg in soil, vastly exceeding the national permissible value of 0.02 mg/kg, indicating a severe contamination issue (Ilić et al., 2021c; Rulebook, 2021).

This situation underscores the critical need for comprehensive cleanup measures and ongoing monitoring to mitigate the health risks and environmental impact. The case of Incel vividly illustrates the broader challenge of managing industrial pollution legacy and emphasizes the importance of robust environmental governance to protect public health and ecosystems.

In July and September 2021, a detailed field investigation of the previously verified seven hotspots in INCEL area and an analytical evaluation of the collected 595 samples of soil and construction debris were carried out. The results of the investigation are described in detail in the report “D2 - Report on Soil Sampling, Laboratory Analyses and Geodetic Survey” submitted to UNDP in October 2021. The results were used as a basis to propose the remediation design

for the INCEL area, presented in detail in the previous chapters of the report (Project/Design, 2021).

The remediation and investigation of the INCEL site in Banja Luka has unveiled a significant level of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) contamination across several hotspots. Through meticulous sampling and analysis, a detailed picture of the site’s environmental challenge has been painted. Below are the key findings and discussions drawn from the investigative efforts:

1. **Extent of PCB Contamination:** The investigation identified PCB concentrations exceeding permissible limits in a substantial portion of the samples. Notably, some areas revealed PCB concentrations as high as 600 mg/kg, signaling severe contamination levels that necessitate immediate remedial action (Project/Design, 2021).
2. **Soil and Groundwater Contamination:** PCB contamination was predominantly found in the upper soil layers, with some locations also showing elevated concentrations at greater depths. This pattern of contamination suggests the potential for further environmental and health risks if not adequately addressed. Groundwater samples confirmed the presence of PCBs, adding another layer of complexity to the remediation efforts due to the potential for contaminant spread through groundwater flow toward the Vrbas River (Project/Design, 2021).
3. **Impact on the Vrbas River Ecosystem:** The investigation extended to the aquatic ecosystem of the Vrbas river, revealing the potential for contamination washout from INCEL hotspots to affect river sediment and, consequently, the benthic organisms, fish, and other higher organisms through bioaccumulation in the food chain (Project/Design, 2021).
4. **Environmental Risk from Rainwater Sewage System:** The environmental risk assessment highlighted the possibility of contaminants spreading through the rainwater sewage system. Sediment samples from the outlet of the sewage system, which discharges rainwater from the INCEL area into the Vrbas river, confirmed increased concentrations of PCBs and other contaminants, underscoring the need for comprehensive measures to prevent further environmental degradation (Project/Design, 2021).
5. **Remediation Efforts:** In response to the findings, short-term preventive measures were promptly implemented to mitigate immediate human health risks. These measures include informing local employees about potential risks, demarcating contaminated areas, and recommending personal protective equipment (PPE) use (Project/Design, 2021).

Additionally, the detailed analysis of contaminated materials facilitated the design of a targeted excavation plan, focusing on areas with the highest levels of contamination for prioritized remediation (Project/Design, 2021).

6. Recommendations for Future Action: Based on the analysis and the scale of contamination, a combination of excavation and ex situ disposal has been recommended as the most effective remediation strategy. This approach is supported by a multi-criteria screening of selected remediation technologies, weighing factors such as human health protection, efficiency, long-term effectiveness, compliance with environmental laws, and cost (Project/Design, 2021).

The hotspot with the highest amount of contaminated material is the Lukić hotspot (former power plant) with a total amount of material for excavation 4,281 m³ (as summarized in the following table). The total amount of contaminated material in the Incel area intended for excavation and subsequent treatment is 4,890 m³.

Table 1 Average and maximum PCBs concentrations and volume of contaminated material to be excavated per each hotspot

Hotspot	Average PCBs (mg/kg d.m.)	Maximum PCBs (mg/kg d.m.)	Volume proposed for excavation (m ³)
Univerzum AD	13.9	113	392
Lukić Invest (former power plant)	3.7 in soil 25.2 in construction debris	2,800 in soil 546 in construction debris	4,281
SHP CELEX AD	3.9	72.8	65
Business zone (electrolysis)	1.7	12	11
Top Metal	0.5	1.08	2
Business zone (in front of BC Metal)	1.8	15.2	102
Business zone (north)	0.22	<5.02	38
Total			4,890

The results of leaching tests show that none of the limit indicators for acceptance of waste to non-hazardous waste landfill (as defined by the European Council Directive 1999/31/EC on the landfill on waste) was exceeded. Thus, it can be stated that contaminated soil and construction debris with the content of PCBs below 50 mg/kg d.m. represented by the collected composite samples (Lukić Invest - former power plant, Business zone - in front of BC Metal and Business zone - Electrolysis) are potentially suitable for disposal at non-hazardous landfills. Nevertheless, the final parameters for waste disposal shall be assessed with regards to local legislation and conditions of the local landfills.

Two groups of contaminated materials are found in INCEL: (1) soil and construction debris with a PCB concentration ≥ 50 mg/kg d.m. and (2) soil and construction debris with a PCB concentration < 50 mg/kg d.m. of PCBs. For each group of contaminated materials, a multi-criteria screening of selected applicable remediation technologies/options has been performed using the following criteria: Protection of human health and the environment, Efficiency, Long-term effectiveness, Compliance with the current environmental laws and regulations, Implement ability, Time and Cost.

Although it is understood that Bosnia and Herzegovina currently do not possess the facilities to dispose of hazardous waste (PCBs ≥ 50 mg/kg d.m.), it is possible that such waste can be exported to a licensed facility abroad. For these reasons and, based on the above information and on the results of the evaluation and screening assessments of potential remedial options (Remediation Assessment Report, Dekonta, 2020), the most recommended option for remediation of contaminated areas at INCEL include excavation and ex situ disposal of contaminated soil and construction materials/debris.

Short-term preventive measures are proposed in the project. They are designed to immediately prevent contact of local employees, visitors and trespassers moving at the contaminated sites (hotspots) with contaminated soil and/or construction materials. The aim of the short-term preventive measures is to minimize human health risks until long-term and permanent remedial measures are implemented.

The remediation project at the INCEL site has highlighted the critical need for comprehensive environmental assessments and targeted remediation strategies to address industrial contamination. The findings underscore the importance of continued monitoring and adaptive management to mitigate the environmental and health risks associated with PCBs and other contaminants.

CONCLUSIONS

The Incel industrial zone in Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina, presents a notable case of environmental contamination, primarily due to the accumulation of polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs) and other hazardous substances in the soil. Recognized as persistent organic pollutants, PCBs pose considerable risks to human health and ecological systems due to their environmental stability and potential for bioaccumulation. Classified as probable human carcinogens, PCBs are linked to numerous health issues, including disorders affecting development, reproduction, the immune system, and neurological functions. The migration of these substances into groundwater, surface water, and even the air through volatilization further exacerbates the risk, affecting the local ecosystem and the respiratory health of nearby populations. Remediation efforts in the Incel zone have been challenging, hindered by the contamination’s complexity, high remediation costs, and legal disputes over pollution responsibility, slowing down the progress.

Concerns from various stakeholders, including residents, environmental organizations, and authorities, have led to calls for enhanced regulatory measures, better waste management, and more rigorous environmental monitoring to mitigate further contamination risks. In response, authorities have introduced stricter industrial controls and waste management improvements, yet significant challenges remain in fully addressing the pollution issues.

This situation underscores the critical need for sustainable industrial practices and responsible waste management to protect community health and the environment. It highlights the essential role of robust environmental regulations and enforcement to ensure industry practices do not compromise ecological and human health. Addressing the contamination at Incel requires a collaborative effort among government, industry, and community stakeholders to develop effective, long-lasting remediation strategies. The comprehensive investigation and remediation efforts at the INCEL site in Banja Luka reveal the profound impact of industrial activities on environmental health and underscore the critical importance of addressing legacy contamination issues. The findings from this project highlight the pervasive nature of PCBs and their potential to inflict significant harm on ecological systems and human health. They also demonstrate the effectiveness of targeted remediation strategies when underpinned by rigorous scientific analysis and a commitment to environmental stewardship. This endeavor stands as a testament to the necessity of integrating environmental science with practical remediation techniques to confront and mitigate the challenges posed by persistent pollutants. It underscores the importance of regulatory

frameworks like the Stockholm Convention in guiding global efforts towards a healthier, more sustainable environment. Furthermore, the project exemplifies the potential for success in environmental restoration efforts, offering valuable lessons for similar projects worldwide.

As we move forward, it is imperative that the international community continues to prioritize the identification, assessment, and remediation of contaminated sites, leveraging both scientific advancements and collaborative efforts to safeguard public health and protect our natural world. The INCEL project not only contributes to the body of knowledge regarding PCB contamination and remediation but also serves as a beacon of hope and a model for future endeavors aiming to heal the scars left by industrial pollution.

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